

Multifocal Versus Ectopic Atrial Tachycardia!

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Description

The above electrocardiogram (EKG) was recorded in a young patient with abdominal pain and palpitations. At first glance the P wave morphology appears to vary, with greater than 3 different morphologies identified as indicated by the different color arrows, suggestive of multifocal atrial tachycardia at 102 beats/minute (BPM). A closer look, however, reveals an initial sinus rhythm (first 2 beats, light green arrows) followed by what seems to be gradual fusion of sinus P waves with ectopic atrial P waves (dark green and light brown arrows), likely a “warm-up period”, with subsequent complete usurpation of the sinus rhythm by an ectopic atrial tachycardia (red arrows).

Discussion

Atrial tachycardia is defined as regular atrial activation from specific isolated sites with centrifugal spread, caused mostly by enhanced

automaticity, and occasionally by triggered activity or micro-reentry [1]. The different anatomic locations and mechanisms of atrial tachycardia can render the arrhythmia resistant to anti-arrhythmic agents, necessitating specialized ablation techniques for more effective control [2].

Multifocal tachycardia is uncommon and often associated with pulmonary disease. Its diagnosis requires 3 different non-sinus P waves separated by isoelectric baseline at a rate > 100 BPM [3]. It is usually responsive to beta blockers such as metoprolol and non-dihydropyridine calcium channel blockers such as verapamil.

In normal hearts, vagally mediated atrial arrhythmias are predominant, as likely in the above case. Sinus rate variability prior to the atrial arrhythmia can be a clue to an autonomic influence, which is crucial to identify whenever antiarrhythmic therapy is ineffective [4].

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